

Impact of Senior Management Support in the Success of electronic Document Management Systems

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Abstract : *The study aimed to identify the commitment of the senior management to develop and support the electronic document management systems and the success of the electronic document management system. In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used the analytical descriptive method in which they tries to describe the phenomenon of the study subject, analyzing its data, the relationship between its components and the opinions that are raised around it. The complete census method was used because of the small size of the study sample and ease of access to the target group. The researchers distributed 108 questionnaires to the Study Population of this research which consist of 65 employees in the Gaza Strip and 43 employees in the West Bank. All the questionnaires were retrieved back.*

The research found the following results: There is weakness about the existence of a special system includes written plan and mechanisms for the management of documents. The work of the Commission focuses largely on documents and their follow-up between departments. The existence of some small computerized systems in some of the departments for document management in the Commission. There is indeed an archive officer. There exist departments competent to manage the archives of the Commission actually. The presence of more than one archive (retirees and participants for each department separately). The adoption of a system of encoding and indexing is unified by the Commission where it is agreed to coding and indexing each type of files. the international standards are not use in the Commission. The absence of procedures and mechanisms for the transfer of documents to the Palestinian National Archives. There is a security plan for documents in the event of disasters where there are fire alarms and the presence of fire extinguishers in the archive on all floors of the Commission.

That there is a commitment by the senior management in the development and support of electronic document management system in all departments and specialties of the Commission, by providing both financial support and the legal boundaries of the electronic system

The research led to a number of recommendations, the most important of which is to increase the interest and awareness of the need to apply policies, mechanisms and procedures to ensure the success of the electronic document management system by taking advantage of the experiences of other institutions and the private sector. The need to enhance attention to the existence of a central computer network linking the main office in Gaza with the rest of the branches in the West Bank in order to ensure the implementation of the electronic document management system and the ability to hold meetings via video screens Convergence and the ability to exchange copies of electronic data. The need to focus on the Palestinian National Archives and follow up the international standards by the International Council for Archives (ICA).

Keywords Senior Management, Electronic Document Management System, Palestinian Pension Authority, State of Palestine.

1. INTRODUCTION

Administrative documents are one of the most important sources of information in modern times. It contains information that does not contain other sources, such as books. These documents are formally produced within official bodies in accordance with official laws and regulations. Document information is therefore accurate and reliable, based on information that is often influenced by the author's attitudes, opinions and culture. Administrative documents record the facts as they occur. The latest information from statistics and reports on some of the topics that may be the subject of research, before they are included in articles, books or even academic theses (Al-Agha, 2007). On the other hand, some of these documents will continue their journey through time by their entitlement to remain as historical witnesses, and thus become an archive deposited in the national archives as the most valuable assets of the country's national history (Abu Naser, & Al Shobaki, 2016), (Abu Naser & Al Shobaki, 2017), (Al Shobaki & Abu Naser, 2017) and (Kassab and others ,2017).

There is no doubt that the administrative documents that are transferred to the eternal preservation of the archival institutions will enter under the auspices of the state, allocate space for them and spend on protecting them and preparing suitable means of finding them. It is therefore necessary to reconcile the process of selection which will result in the selection of collections of documents that will become part of the archives' archival, and even part of the nation's heritage and the sources of its history and civilization (Al-Sharif, 2002).

In the last decades of the twentieth century, with the emergence and evolution of the computer emerged new methods other than the traditional methods to save the necessary documents and archived through the use of computer memory- digital memory- and the development of this new method with the development of automation and digital memory capacity and development of software reduction and preservation and retrieval of information and documents (Hamouda, 2003), and the importance of the Commission's need for staff files, the development of an electronic document management system is one of the most important things that must occur as soon as possible, as researchers see it.

2. RESEARCH PROBLEM

It is clear that the Palestinian Pension Authority is on the verge of a new phase after the launch of its electronic documents archiving project. It met with Ezzeddine (2004) that the size of the archives is increasing in inflation; the average number of papers per file is 200 documents in different sizes, dealing with the current archiving system, increasing its costs, and the possibility of exposing some of the contents of the file to be lost after being reviewed by the specialist, and the damage is sure to get paper documents makes it more complicated to use, and the urgent need of these historical paper files are concentrated in that they constitute an administrative information system. Thus integrating these files with the electronic records on the PPA database (Abu Naser, & Al Shobaki, 2016), (Abu Naser & Al Shobaki, 2017), (Al Shobaki & Abu Naser, 2017) and (Kassab and others ,2017).

**The problem of the study is to answer the following main research question:
What is the impact of senior management's support in success of the electronic document management systems?**

3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The research hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H1: There is a statistically significant impact of the commitment of the senior management to develop and support the electronic document management system on the success of the electronic document management system in the Palestinian Pension Authority.

4. STUDY LIMITS AND SCOPE

- **Subject (Academic) limitations:** The objective of the research was to study the commitment of the senior management to develop and support the electronic document management system and the success of the electronic document management system.
- **Human Limitations:** The research was conducted on the employees of the Palestinian Pension Authority.
- **Institutional Limit:** The study was conducted in the Palestinian Pension Authority.
- **Place Limitations:** The study was conducted in the State of Palestine, and was limited to the Palestinian Pension Authority.
- **Temporal limitation:** Research and preliminary data collection were conducted during the year (2017).

5. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The aim of this research is to achieve the following objectives:

- Highlight the importance of commitment and support of senior management in the development of electronic document management system.
- Statement of the impact of senior management support for the use of the electronic document system
- Identify senior management's commitment to the availability of technical infrastructure in the organization (software, equipment and communications).
- Recognize the commitment of senior management to provide training and development for employees of electronic document management system.
- The role of senior management by providing expertise and external consultation to support the success of electronic document management system.
- Explore the role of senior management in developing policies, mechanisms and procedures to work on the electronic document management system.
- To highlight the role of the Palestinian Pension Authority in developing its technological sustainability.
- Outcome and recommendations contribute to the development of Palestinian governmental institutions.

6. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

The study to adapt and interact with rapid environmental changes through a strategic plan involving all parties dealing with the university.

- This research draws on its importance as it is characterized by modernity and scientific and practical excellence.

- This is the first research on the level of Palestine in terms of authenticity, resurgence and scarcity of research on its subject, which necessitates enriching the subject with research and studies because of its great importance in our daily lives.
- Recognize the importance and role of senior management in the development and support of electronic document management system and impact on the success of electronic document management system, and the consequent saving of time and effort.
- This research is an incentive for senior management in the Authority to start technical development processes in all administrative areas.
- The scarcity of local studies related to the study of the role of senior management in supporting and implementing electronic document management system or in relation to the study of electronic archiving.
- Senior management in the Palestinian Retirement Authority can greatly benefit from the study to develop its document management system, which helps them save time, effort and costs as well as increase productivity and performance.
- Study the role of senior management in working on the current document management system and identify the disadvantages and try to develop solutions; which will show the advantages of using modern systems in the management of electronic documents and benefits to ensure the rapid delivery of services to users.
- To attempt to enable the senior management of the Authority to develop its technological capabilities in order to link them with e-government. This meets with this research regarding the exchange of electronic data and the availability of technological infrastructure, and also that electronic archiving should be one of the main parts of the e-government project.

7. PREVIOUS STUDIES

Study of (Farwana, 2016) aimed at identifying the impact of the ICT sector on the Palestinian Gross Domestic Product(GDP) during the period 2000-2014 through the analytical descriptive approach and the use of the standard method to clarify the relationships between the independent variables (fixed telephone number, Mobile phone, Internet users, number of employees, intermediate consumption, production, employee compensation, number of operating establishments). The dependent variable of economic growth measured by the Palestinian GDP. The study found that there is a positive relationship between the variables related to the number of mobile phones and intermediate consumption. The contribution of some variables is significant and consistent with the economic theory. As for the other variables, it is clear that these variables are not significant with the rest of the variables due to the short chain used in the model and the modern technology sector Information and communications. Based on the results of the study, the researcher recommends focusing on the ICT sector as this sector is considered an important and effective sector in the Palestinian economy, especially as the Palestinian situation is under occupation and as the only economy able to overcome the economic and political conditions in the Palestinian economy. The role of scientific and research institutions in creating a developed Palestinian economy capable of advancing and keeping pace with the global developments in the ICT sector.

The study of (Lubad, 2016), which aims to identify the elements of the success of the application of e-government in Palestine through the mixed methodology (descriptive- quantitative) using questionnaire and interviews as tools for study. The study sample consisted of 234 questionnaires obtained randomly from the study population, which is composed of senior management in the ministries in the West Bank and the Gaza Strip in addition to interviews with specialists from the government, the Legislative Council and civil society institutions. The study found the necessary elements for the success of e-government applications as well as the obstacles facing the applications in Palestine. The most important elements of the success of the applications were the availability of vision, administrative and technical structure, human resources, adequate laws and legislation, e-government awareness and services, and civil society institutions. The absence of unity of efforts between the West Bank and the Gaza Strip, weak involvement of senior management in the ministries and civil society institutions enough in the planning and implementation, In addition to a weakness in the administrative and technical aspects and the lack of adequate laws and legislation covering all areas of e-government, the need for specialized human resources and lack of awareness about e-government services. The study concluded a number of recommendations, the most important of which are the necessity of unifying the strategy and geology of e-government applications between the West Bank and the Gaza Strip. Senior management in ministries in the planning and implementation process, enacting adequate laws and legislation to cover issues related to e-government, the need for administrative reform and provision of technical requirements, development of human cadres, and educating citizens about e-government and its services.

Study of (Hamada, 2014) aimed at understanding the role of electronic transactions in the development of government performance in terms of increasing efficiency and effectiveness, enhancing transparency and increasing the quality of government services. The aim of this study is to know the availability of e-transactions requirements in the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology. In addition to identifying the most important problems facing the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology in the process of transition to electronic transactions. The researcher used the descriptive analytical method and used the Complete Census method. The questionnaire was distributed to all 111 members of the study population. The study

reached several results, the most important of which is that the requirements for the implementation of electronic transactions in the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology related to administrative requirements, technical structure, financial resources and qualified human cadres trained in computerized applications and systems are available. The study also showed that most of the ministry's services are provided through electronic transactions, in addition to a positive relationship between the application of electronic transactions and the development of performance through increasing efficiency and efficiency, enhancing transparency and improving public service. The study issued a number of recommendations, including the need to enhance the skills and abilities of the staff required to implement electronic transactions through a training plan, and the development of appropriate mechanisms to advertise electronic transactions through marketing and advertising means, and the need to provide an electronic payment system.

Study of (Abassi, 2012) aimed to identify the importance of the transformation from the traditional administrative systems to the digital administrative systems. It has reached several conclusions that there is a relationship between the nature of the company's work and its need to implement digital management systems. The application of digital management systems also requires flexibility in the organizational structure and communication process in the company, Dedicated financial allocations are barriers that slow the adoption of digital management systems, and digital management systems change the nature of operations and the way the company performs. It has recommended the need for good planning and preparing employees, supporting, activating the marketing information systems in the company, linking them with all departments to increase the market share, applying the transformation strategy to all branches, and linking them with the main center.

Study of (Alaloul, 2011), which aims to identify the availability of the requirements of the success of the application of electronic administration in the top 100 charitable societies in the Gaza Strip and its impact on institutional preparedness against corruption. The researcher used the analytical descriptive method. The researcher also prepared a questionnaire for the purpose of research as a main tool. It was distributed to the managers of the top 100 charitable societies with 100% recovery rate. In addition, four interviews were conducted to explain some of the results. The success of applying electronic administration in the major charities in the Gaza Strip by 68.92%, as they become more available in the internal processes of the association and decrease in relation to the public. This reduces the realism of the application of electronic administration in the full level of service delivery to the external public, The charitable organizations in the Gaza Strip enjoy institutional preparedness against corruption by 76.68%. This ratio reduces corruption but does not prevent it, especially in light of the low level of corruption. Appropriate income, and with insufficient degree of integrity values, which may transform transparency, accountability and accountability into formal and public actions that are disguised by corrupt practices. The study concluded several recommendations for the various parties concerned, the most important of which are: The need for charities to include the application of electronic management adequately in the strategic and operational plans of the association, and to focus on the involvement of relevant parties and to motivate and train employees to achieve successful implementation, fortifying them with licensed, integrated information security programs, gradually developing the association's website to interact with the public, and provide services.

The study of (Marghalani, 2010) aims to identify the trends of the employees of the General Organization for Social Insurance in Jeddah towards the application of the electronic trading system and has reached several results, the most important of which is the security and information technology security, the electronic security system in the work is Non-intrusive with a low degree. Electronic transactions have effectively contributed to the exchange of information between departments, and the information provided by the electronic transaction system for employees is correct and clear. It recommended the need for diversity in the use of modern techniques in management information systems, to increase the level of safety, confidentiality of data and information, to rehabilitate employees through internal, and external scholarships.

The study of (Al-Masri, 2007) aimed at identifying the requirements of the use of electronic signature in the management of information technology centers in the Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip represented in (IT infrastructure development, the attention of the senior management of the Information Technology Center using electronic signature, legal and legislative use of electronic signature, adoption of electronic correspondence and policies to protect electronic information) also the study aimed to clarify the importance of maintaining the security of information and the use of advanced technology in the protection of privacy through correspondence only Electronic. Where the researcher used the descriptive analytical method, where the study population of all staff of information technology centers in the Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip, has been relying on the questionnaire to collect data. The study concluded that the electronic signature technology is not used in information technology centers in the Palestinian universities in the Gaza Strip, and that the equipment and security software used in information technology centers need to be updated to be able to protect electronic information efficiently and IT centers staff have limitations to the concept of electronic signature. The study issued several recommendations, the most important of which is that the administration of the Palestinian universities needs to adopt the official e-mail using electronic signature, updating the security equipment and developing the information security software currently used in IT centers, allocating an annual budget for information security and training IT staff in the field of information security, the development of information security policies and using the electronic signature on an ongoing basis in information technology centers.

The study of (Panajah, 2006) aimed at presenting the experience of the Emirate of Makkah Region in the application of the electronic archive, in addition to identifying the obstacles and difficulties faced by the Emirate during the transition to electronic archives. It has come out with a set of results, the most important of which is that the electronic archiving of documents in the Emirate of Makkah region has helped to raise the efficiency of work and performance better and open new horizons in providing government services to citizens and other departments. The study also recommended the necessity of continuing the effort to complete the electronic archive in the Emirate and linking it to the internal network and the database of the institutions so that it can be utilized by all the departments operating in the Emirate, with the necessity of cooperation between governmental and non governmental bodies within the country in the field of information management in the electronic age.

8. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

8.1 Concept of electronic documents

Information is no longer just a kind of luxury, which boasts communities or institutions, but has become a cornerstone in the development of society and achieve the desired well-being, and has entered the information and communication technology all fields of social science and humanity, our present and future era is the age of electronic information in the service of society. It is essential for maximizing human thought and mind with computers, networks, modern means of communication, artificial intelligence and expert systems.

The electronic document system is similar to any manual document archiving system in terms of the general structure of document archiving tools including Cabinet, Drawer, Folder, Files, Documents, and Scanner . DIRKS (Designing and Implementing Recordkeeping Systems) defines electronic archiving as the process of manufacturing and maintaining a reliable and complete directory of business movements in the organization.

The management information systems dealing with data and documents that exceed one of the original sources of the organization, whether produced by the organization in the context of its work or receive through the external environment that deal with. This data and documents are dealt with through the information system of the organization set up plans and operating procedures and trading, adjust the flow paths data and documents the organization by adjusting the documentary cycle, procedures for performing administrative activities, while facilitating the means of control of these procedures, follow-up implementation, so we find that the objective of the information systems did not only carry out monitoring, collection, treatment and storage, but it is the ultimate goal in the retrieval, trading operations, broadcasting selective information and documents when needed to beneficiary communities end user, where cutting-edge systems are designed to provide immediate and accurate answers in the light of the documents and data stored in the database. As well as automating the procedures to save time and effort and ensure confidentiality when trading where the paths through which the procedures are accomplished within each department in the organization through the so-called electronic document system, which deals with the management of data and documents within the organization since its establishment or reception until completion. Thus avoid making many manual archive problems (Simon and others, 1998).

8.2 Objectives of electronic archiving

The long-term strategic goal of e-archiving is to achieve a paperless environment, an e-government, no queues, no paper documents. The immediate goal of the organization is to counter the massive flow of documents and control of archival stocks Stacked, processed, saved and retrieved in the fastest times that respond to the speed of the times (Al-Jahimi, 2001).

Electronic archiving will help to quickly process documents indexed automatically and saved in more than one original and the distribution of these "originals" to the various parties involved, and therefore no longer afraid of the employee's slow access to the document. The retrieval of the document has become more rapid and in a more varied way. The unordered document is in the documentation of the lost information. How can a person control the order and save millions of documents today without a system such as the electronic archive system?

8.3 Advantages of electronic documents (automatic archiving)

(Al-Salemi and others, 2005): The elimination of the problems of preservation and manual handling of files resulting in damage, loss, theft or other risks of manual trading. Participation at the level of the subject file, documents and data related to the subjects. Eliminate conservation problems and save up to 90% of space. Define a password for each user. Define a password for each archive and each software application within the organization. Identify paths for document cycles between more than one user. Defines the path attachments on which documents are passed. The speed of trading, retrieval, broadcasting, and the transfer of documents and information to others in various locations. Manage the documentary cycle from the beginning until the completion of all procedures and the possibility of following all the procedures on the network, and print the report on all stages of the documentary cycle. Fast access to the substantive content of files and information directly as a result of classification and indexing systems used. Access to

reports, statistics and comparison tables easily and easily through databases containing data and all related documents and documents of the Organization. Eliminate the geographical and temporal interval between categories of beneficiaries to meet their immediate information and documentation needs. Make contacts with others at the same time without problems in broadcasting documents and information. Integrate and coordinate the circulation of documents and information within or outside the organization. Provide the opportunity to deal with workers with the technical systems of documents and information at the international level through their dealings with other local and international organizations. Provide selective broadcast services for information and documents as soon as data and documents are updated. To confirm the credibility and validity of the technical systems of documents and information when dealing with others with high confidence. Accuracy, speed, insurance and preservation of files and information against all types of risks with alternative versions in multiple locations. Save time and effort and rationalize financial spending to optimize the utilization of available economic resources (Kassab and others ,2017).

9. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND PROCEDURES

First: Research Methodology:

In order to achieve the objective of the study, the researchers used the descriptive analytical method in the study because it is appropriate to the phenomenon in question. The researchers also used primary and secondary sources to collect data for the study. The primary data were processed using statistical analysis methods suitable for the study objectives: frequency distribution, arithmetic mean, through the use of SPSS statistical program and the extraction of results.

Second: Society and sample of the study:

The study population consists of all 128 employees of the Palestinian Authority (Gaza Strip - West Bank) who hold administrative positions. The number of 20 employees in service positions (guard, reporter, driver, utility) has been excluded because their responses are not of research value in relation to Research topic. Table (1) shows the distribution of the population and the sample of the research by regions

Table 1: Distribution of Population and sample by region

No.	Region	Number of Employees
1.	Gaza strip	80
2.	West Bank (Ramallah)	48
Total		128

Source: Prepared by the researchers depending on the Commission statistics, 2017

In table 1, the researchers used the comprehensive Complete Census method in the distribution of the questionnaire. The questionnaires were distributed to the administration in the Authority. These are the following names: Head of the Commission with the rank of Minister, Director General, Director of Department, Head of Department, Head of Division, (108) distributed the questionnaire as follows: (65) employees in the head office of the Authority in the Gaza Strip, and (43) Staff in the Authority's headquarters in Ramallah and Hebron - The West Bank represents the study community, so the researchers used a comprehensive Complete Census method in the distribution of the questionnaire. (108) questionnaires were retrieved and analyzed.

Statistical description of the research sample according to personal characteristics and characteristics

The following is a description of the characteristics of the research sample according to gender, the nature of the job, the scientific qualification, the number of years of service, and specialization in the Authority under study.

Table 2: Statistical description of the research sample according to personal characteristics and characteristics (n = 108)

Characteristics and personality traits		Repetition	Percentage	ranking
Gender	Male	78	72.22	1
	female	30	27.78	2

Nature of the job	make a decision	1	0.9	4
	Consulting	4	3.7	3
	Administrative	98	90.7	1
	Other	5	4.6	2
Qualification	Secondary and lower	12	11.1	2
	Diploma	6	5.5	2
	BA	82	75.9	1
	Postgraduate	8	7.4	3
Number of years of service	5-1	19	17.5	2
	10-6	40	37.0	1
	15-11	14	12.9	4
	16 and more	35	32.4	3
Specialization	Administrative and economic sciences	68	62.9	1
	Engineering / Information Technology	14	12.9	4
	Legal sciences	6	5.5	3
	Other	20	18.5	2

Table (2) shows that males accounted for 72.22% of the total study population, the researchers believe the presence of the functions of the Commission in need of high physical abilities because of work and continuity of the size, and therefore management in these tasks tend to appoint male more than female and this is in line with study of (Abu Awaily, 2007) where he reached the element ratio of male to 92.75%, while females accounted for 27.78% of the total sample and this high ratio compared with the study of (Abu Awaily, 2007) the researchers believe that the nature of the work of the female of direct their handling of documents and internal correspondence and Foreign Affairs, disagreed with the study of (Abu Awaily, 2007) that the Commission sometimes subject to what other ministries subject to by the assignment of female from General Personnel, and favoritism in recruitment.

The percentage of decision-making function was 0.9% of the total study population. This indicates that only the head of the committee has the decision, whereas the percentage of consultancy posts was 3.7% of the total sample. With the objectives of the research so that the focus of work in the Commission on the administrative category.

The percentage of employees with a public secondary school is less than 11.1% of the total research community, and researchers believe that this proportion is a little high, researchers may be attributed to the reason for the rise of a small proportion that the holders of these qualifications are of large ages, in this case, most of the staff are busy. The percentage of those with an average diploma is 5.5% of the total sample. Most of them are between the ages of 35-45. The researchers believe that the owners of this group worked in the early establishment of the Commission and they have good practical experience. The percentage of those with a bachelor's degree and above was 75.9% of the total sample, which is high. The researchers believe that the increase in the number of universities in Palestine gave more opportunities for students to obtain a bachelor's degree. Encouraged many of the diploma holders or less to obtain it, and also indicates the extent of encouragement of the Commission for scientific development, and the Commission provided financial support to all graduate students at local or foreign universities (Abu Naser, & Al Shobaki, 2016), (Abu Naser & Al Shobaki, 2017), (Al Shobaki & Abu Naser, 2017) and (Kassab and others ,2017).

The percentage of employees with less than 6 years of service is 17.5% of the total sample, while the percentage of those with years of experience from 6-10 years is 37.0% of the total sample. The researchers believe that this high percentage is the most important work of the Commission. The percentage of those with years of experience from 11-15 years was 12.9% of the total sample. The percentage of those with 16 years of experience or more was 32.4% of the total sample. In view of these percentages, 82.3% of the sample members have sufficient years of experience in their fields of work. Therefore, the researchers believe that this

will increase confidence in the results of this research. This is in line with the research objectives. This is consistent with Abu Awaily (2007), where the percentage of those with sufficient experience to perform tasks over 5 years is 91.1%.

The proportion of employees with a specialization in administrative and economic sciences is 62.9% of the total sample, while the proportion of employees obtaining the specialization of engineering / information technology 12.9% of the total sample, and the proportion of employees with a specialization in legal sciences 5.5% of the total sample, Employees with other specialties 18.5% of the total sample. In view of these percentages, we find that the largest proportion of the sample items have a specialization in administrative and economic sciences, which indicates the extent of the Authority's keenness to select its cadres to be suitable for the nature of the work they are practicing. This is in line with the study of Abu Khalaf (2001) adapting to the transformation of the University's manual processes into electronic. Therefore, after identifying their work, we find that it relies heavily on the current document management system. Because of the increasing workload and the number of termination files (Madenin, the security forces, the PLO), we suffer from slow processing of files Termination of service In each department of the Commission, especially in the settlement and drainage, which is the bottleneck in the life of the file; in order to determine the type of benefit to be obtained by the pensioner and the mother (pension and reward, only pension, reward only), so researchers believe that the Commission urgently need an Electronic document management system that works to manage, organize, facilitate, speed up and reliability of file handling.

10. STUDY TOOL

The researchers used a data collection designed to achieve the objectives of the study by collecting the necessary data. The answers for each paragraph in the five-digit Likert model were as follows:

Category	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Points	5	4	3	2	1

Statistical Methods:

To analyze the data and achieve the collected research objectives, the computer has been used in the analysis and processing of data through many appropriate statistical methods using statistical packages for social sciences (SPSS). The following is a set of statistical methods used in data analysis:

- Percentages and frequencies.
- Alpha Cronbach test to confirm the stability of the questionnaire paragraphs.
- Split-half test was used to measure the stability of the questionnaire paragraphs and the value was improved using the Spearman Brown equation.
- Colmgruff-Smarnov test to see if the data follow normal distribution or not.
- Sign test to test the questionnaire paragraphs.
- Use the Spearman correlation coefficient to demonstrate hypotheses.
- Krustal-Wallis Test to see if there are significant differences between the opinions of the sample members due to personal differences (age, nature of job, specialization, qualification, number of years of service).

The validity and stability of the study

The researchers conducted a number of tests on the questionnaire to ensure their validity and stability of the questionnaire through experts in the field in addition to the statistical tests necessary to verify the validity and stability.

Validity of the study tool

The internal consistency of the questionnaire was calculated on a 30-questionnair survey sample by calculating the correlation coefficient value between each paragraph and the total value of the axis, as well as the internal consistency calculation by calculating the correlation coefficient value between each axis and the total value of the axes.

Calculation of correlation coefficient

Table 7: Calculation of the correlation coefficient and the moral level between the value of each paragraph and the total value of the paragraphs "The commitment of senior management in development and support of electronic document management system"

No.	Paragraph	Coefficient of correlation	Moral level
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No.	Paragraph	Coefficient of correlation	Moral level
1.	The Commission has the appropriate plans and policies on the electronic document management system and is specific to specific objectives.	0.700**	0.000
2.	Senior management is committed to implementing plans and policies related to electronic document management system.	0.744**	0.000
3.	Senior management provides financial support for the success of the electronic document management system.	0.751**	0.000
4.	Senior management disseminates the culture and benefits of the electronic document management system.	0.747**	0.000
5.	Senior management is concerned with the global technological development in the field of management and the use of electronic documents.	0.837**	0.000
6.	Senior management encourages e-business and lack of trust in manual work.	0.783**	0.000
7.	Senior management provides legal boundaries within the TRA to work through the electronic document system, such as signing and archiving.	0.675**	0.000
8.	Directors, department heads and heads of divisions have knowledge of the nature of electronic document management	0.740**	0.000
9.	The experiences of other institutions and companies were reviewed in order to benefit from the implementation of electronic document management system.	0.670**	0.000

**The correlation was statistically significant ($\alpha = 0.01$)

Ttable 7 shows the correlation coefficients between each of the axes of the first axis and the total value of the axial segments, indicating that the correlation coefficients are significant at the level of $\alpha = 0.01$.

Structural validity of the dimensions of the test

Table 8: Calculation of the correlation coefficient and the level of the significance of each axis of the axes with the total score of the questionnaire paragraphs

No.	Paragraph	Coefficient of correlation	Moral level
1.	Senior management commitment to development and support of electronic document management system	0.659**	0.000**
2.	The importance of electronic document management system and its advantages	0.631**	0.000**
3.	Provides the technical background (dealing with computers and peripherals) and the level of education of employees	0.591**	0.000**
4.	Recruiting the latest computers and peripherals	0.627**	0.000**
5.	Employment of the latest database and software applications (Software and Database)	0.665**	0.000**
6.	Employing the latest technology in the field of networking and communications	0.630**	0.000**
7.	Develop policies, mechanisms and procedures for the implementation of electronic document management system	0.471**	0.000**
8.	The success of the electronic document management system in the Commission	0.482**	0.000**

**The correlation was statistically significant ($\alpha = 0.01$)

Table 8 shows correlation coefficients between the value of each axis and the total value of the questionnaires, indicating that the correlation coefficients are significant ($\alpha = 0.01$) which indicates the veracity of the questionnaire paragraphs to measure the target for which they were set.

Stability of the study tool

The researchers performed the stability steps on the sample of the exploratory study in two ways: the first is the alpha-cronbach method and the second is the half-split method.

First: alpha Cronbach's method

Table 9: Stability coefficients using alpha Cronbach coefficient method

Paragraph	Number of paragraphs	Alpha Cronbach coefficient
Senior management commitment to development and support of electronic document management system	9	0.902

Table 9 shows that stability coefficients are high.

Second: Split-half Coefficient

The value of the Spearman correlation coefficient was found between the odd numbered and even numbered questions for each axis of the questionnaire. The value of the coefficients was corrected using the Spearman Brown coefficient of correction according to the following equation:

$$\text{Spearman-Brown Coefficient} = \frac{2r}{1+r}$$

Table 10: Split-half Coefficient

Paragraph	Number of paragraphs	Coefficient of correlation	Correlation coefficient corrected
Senior management commitment to development and support of electronic document management system	9	0.695	0.820

Table 10 shows that stability coefficients are relatively high.

11. INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS OF STUDY AXES AND HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Natural distribution test (Kolmajarov-Smarnov test 1-Sample K-S)

The Kolmajarov-Smarnov test was used to determine whether the data followed normal distribution. It is a necessary test in the case of hypothesis testing.

Table 11: One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

Paragraph	Test value Z	Moral level
Senior management commitment to development and support of electronic document management system	1.966	0.001

Table 11 shows the results of the test as the value of the significance level is less than 0.05 (sig. <0.05). This indicates that the data do not follow normal distribution.

12. ANALYSIS OF PARAGRAPHS OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE

The following tables show the percentage of alternatives for each paragraph as well as the mean, the relative weight and the sig value of each paragraph. Since the data are descriptive, the researchers used the sign test, which is a non-parametric test that matches the nature of the ordinal data. (N) "the number of members of the study community greater than the neutral value (3)" which is greater than the value of (N) "the number of members of the study community is less than the neutral value (3)" and the moral level is less than or equal to (0.05), the paragraph is negative in the sense that members of the study community do not agree to (N) "the number of members of the study community below the neutral value (3)" is greater than the value of (N) "the number of members of the study community is greater than the neutral value (3)" and the moral level is less than or equal to (0.05). The level of significance was greater than (0.05) indicating that the value is centered around the neutral value (3).

Testing the question of the study

The answer of the main research question: What is the impact of senior management's commitment to developing and supporting the electronic document management system on the success of electronic document management system?

Analysis of the paragraphs of the questionnaire:

Table 12: Distribution of the Study Community

No.	Paragraph	SMA	Relative weight	Moral level	Ranking
1.	There is a special system that includes written plan and document management mechanisms	3.07	61.4	0.000	4
2.	The movement of the documents issued by the Authority and to which they are sent shall be monitored	4.67	93.4	0.000	1
3.	A computerized document management system (outbound and inbound management)	2.94	58.8	0.000	5
4.	There is a scientifically qualified archiving officer who is responsible for managing archives at the Commission	2.56	51.2	0.000	6
5.	There is a department specialized in managing the archives of the Authority	3.45	68.9	0.000	2
6.	There is a unified classification system in document management in the Commission	1.75	35.1	0.000	8
7.	There is a unified coding system and indexing in document management in the Commission	3.24	64.8	0.000	3
8.	ISO-15489 is used in document management	1.47	29.4	0.000	10
9.	There are procedures and mechanisms for the transfer of documents to the Palestinian National Archives	1.47	29.4	0.000	9
10.	There is a plan for document security in the event of disasters (fire, etc.)	1.79	35.8	0.000	7
11.	I have received any training in document management and archiving	1.26	25.2	0.000	11

From the above table, the researchers conclude that the percentage of employees who agreed to a special system that includes a written plan and document management mechanisms is 38.6% of the total sample. The percentage of employees who agreed that the movement of documents issued by the Commission to which they are referred is 81.4% of the total sample. This percentage indicates that the work in the Authority focuses heavily on the documents and their follow-up among the departments. The percentage of employees who agreed that a computerized document management system is used is 35.7% of the total sample. This indicates that there are some computerized small systems on the Microsoft Access databases in some of the departments for document management. The percentage of staff who agreed that there is a scientific and specialized archiving officer to manage the archive in the Commission is 25.7% of the total sample, which indicates that there is an archiving officer.

As the researchers conclude from the previous table, the percentage of employees who agreed that there is a specialized department to manage the archives of the Authority is 50.0% of the total sample. The percentage of employees who agreed that there is a unified classification system in the management of documents in the Commission is 28.6% of the total sample, which is almost low because there is more than one archive (for retirees, participants and for each department separately). The percentage of employees who agreed that there is a unified coding system and indexing in document management in the Commission is 41.5% of the total sample. This is a high percentage due to the adoption of a coding and indexing system that is unified by the Authority, where the coding and indexing of each type of file is agreed upon. The percentage of staff who agreed that ISO-15489 is used in document management is 4.3% of the total sample. This percentage is very low due to the non-use of these international standards in the Commission.

The researchers also conclude that the percentage of staff who agreed that there are procedures and mechanisms for the transfer of documents to the Palestinian National Archives is 4.3% of the total sample, which is very low due to the lack of use of these procedures and mechanisms in the Commission. The percentage of staff who agreed that there is a disaster security plan is 14.3% of the total sample, which is very low due to the existence of fire alarms, alarms and the existence of fire extinguishers in the archives and on all floors of the Commission. The percentage of staff who received training in document management and archiving is 2.8%

of the total sample, which is very low because of some of the training and after discussion with these employees, researchers found that they received training in document management and archiving in the era of the Israeli Civil Administration of the Gaza Strip.

Analysis of the study paragraphs:

Table 12 presents the views of the study population on the commitment of senior management in development and support of the electronic document management system. These answers are arranged according to their importance according to the arithmetic mean and relative weight. They reflect the commitment of senior management in development and support of electronic document management system, As the mean value increases the commitment of senior management in development and support the electronic document management system increase the attention to them, which directly affects the success of the implementation of electronic document management system in the Commission.

Table 13: Analysis of the "extent of commitment of senior management in development and support of electronic document management system"

No.	Paragraph	SMA	Relative weight	Moral level	Ranking
1.	The Commission has the appropriate plans and policies on the electronic document management system and is specific to specific objectives.	3.29	65.8	0.000	6
2.	Senior management is committed to implementing plans and policies related to electronic document management system.	3.37	67.4	0.000	4
3.	Senior management provides financial support for the success of the electronic document management system.	3.77	75.4	0.000	1
4.	Senior management disseminates the culture and benefits of the electronic document management system.	2.94	58.8	0.000	8
5.	Senior management is concerned with the global technological development in the field of management and the use of electronic documents.	3.47	69.4	0.000	3
6.	Senior management encourages e-business and lack of trust in manual work.	3.34	66.8	0.000	5
7.	Senior management provides legal boundaries within the TRA to work through the electronic document system, such as signing and archiving.	3.56	71.2	0.000	2
8.	Directors, department heads and heads of divisions have knowledge of the nature of electronic document management.	3.07	61.4	0.000	7
9.	The experiences of other institutions and companies were reviewed in order to benefit from the implementation of electronic document management system.	2.63	52.6	0.000	9
Total		3.27	65.4	0.000	

The researchers conclude from Table (13) that:

The section "Senior Management provides financial support for the success of electronic document management system" ranked first, with 55.7% approval of the study community. The relative weight of this item was 75.4%. This paragraph has a high relative weight is indicative of its importance in comparison with the other paragraphs. This is an indication that all staff agree that the material element is the basis for the success of the electronic system, because the Insurance and Pensions Fund is independent and has its own legal personality and budget and a Board of Management and Pensions, (Law of Insurance and Pensions, 1999); a result of this attention will lead to laying the foundation for the success of the electronic document management system.

- In the second section, the top management provided legal boundaries within the organization to work through the electronic document system, such as signing and saving. In this regard, 57.1% of the study community agreed in terms of importance compared to the other paragraphs, where the relative weight was 71.2%. This is an indication of the confidence of the staff that the existence of legal boundaries to work in the system ensures its success significantly, and this indicates the awareness and awareness of employees of the importance of working within legal limits.

- The top management of the world's technological development in the field of management and the use of electronic documents ranked third, with 51.5% of the members of the study community in terms of importance compared to the other paragraphs. The relative weight was 69.4%. The Authority is using the modern means of management and this is reflected in the Commission's commitment to the standards of the International Social Security Association (ISSA) and continues to contact them through attending conferences and discussing the latest topics. The administration has also attended several conferences and seminars regarding pension systems, Informatics in Jordan, Egypt, Morocco, Tanzania, France, America and several other countries, this ratio is relatively high and reflects the interest of the Department in keeping up with technological development in order to use modern methods in management.
- The paragraph "Senior management is committed to implementing the plans and policies related to the electronic document management system" ranked fourth, with the approval of (42.8%) of the members of the study community in terms of importance compared to other paragraphs. The relative weight of this paragraph was 67.4% knowledge of the existence of staff policies and plans for implementation to ensure the success of the electronic document management system.
- The paragraph " senior management encourages to work online and lack of confidence in manual work" ranked fifth, (47.2%) of the members of the study community assure that. This paragraph ranked fifth in terms of importance compared with other paragraphs. The relative weight of this paragraph was 66.8%. This is an indication of the importance of this paragraph and its relation to the subject of the study. This paragraph is relatively few and the reason is the second part of the paragraph "lack of confidence in manual work", where researchers believe the existence of a class of employees believe the negative part of this and urges the existence of great confidence in manual work if working together with the electronic system
- The paragraph "The Commission has the appropriate plans and policies on the electronic document management system with specific objectives" was approved by 42.8% of the members of the study community. This section ranked sixth in terms of importance compared to other paragraphs. The relative weight of this section was 65.8% The researchers believe that the significance of the sixth order instead of the fourth; because the implementation of plans more important than the availability and numbers, and most of the staff of the Commission do not know about the provision of plans for the electronic document management system of senior management.
- The results of the analysis of the paragraph "Managers, heads of departments and heads of divisions have knowledge of the nature of electronic document management" showed that they obtained approval by (38.6%) of the members of the study society. This paragraph ranked seventh in terms of importance compared with other paragraphs. And this paragraph attempts to identify the heads of departments and heads of the people of the nature of the management of electronic documents only and focused on this category of the most important Its executive management in the work of the Commission.
- 35.7% of the study community agreed that the senior management disseminates the culture of the use of electronic document management system and its benefits and advantages in the work of the Commission in particular or at the general level. This section ranked fourth in terms of importance compared to other paragraphs, Relative to this paragraph 58.8%. The researchers believe that this percentage is considered very low compared to the other percentages. This is because there are no workshops or awareness programs in the Commission about the electronic document management system and on the other side of the lack of actual participation in planning the system.(Al-Ghouti, 2006). The e-Government project lacked awareness programs regarding a decline in the culture of managers and heads of departments.
- The results of the study showed that 27.1% of the study society agreed that the senior management reviewed the experiences of other institutions and companies in order to benefit from the implementation of the electronic document management system in the Authority. This section ranked ninth and final in terms of importance. 52.6%. The researchers believe that this percentage is considered very low compared to other ratios. This is due to the fact that there is no central government presence such as e-government or a Commission responsible for e-government transactions in order to coordinate and enable the Commission to review the experiences of institutions (E-government project - Ministry of Communications, 2003). In addition, there is a clear indication that the employees did not know the future interest of the organization and its aspirations and did not involve a large percentage of them in planning or studying the system. This is contrary to the Working Group (2002) study on the need to deal with the private sector as an essential partner in electronic transactions and e-government.

The researchers conclude that in general arithmetic average of all the paragraphs on "the extent of senior management's commitment to the development and support of electronic document management system" 3:27 relative weight 65.4% and the level of moral (0.000), which is less than 0.05, indicating that there is a commitment by the senior management Commission in the field of development and support of electronic document management accepted by the system, the researchers believe that the reason for the decline this percentage is not put to proceed to the application of electronic document management system in the Commission, and

poor dissemination of the culture of the use of electronic document management system between the staff Commission, poor access to the experiences of appropriate mechanisms Other institutions and the private sector with regard to electronic document management system, poor provision of plans for a system of electronic document management - to now and therefore a weakness of the staff in the answer to some of the paragraphs of this axis, agreed community study by good that senior management has the ability to provide financial support , the provision of legal limits, providing the most technologically advanced tools for the application of electronic document management system, which emphasizes that senior management's commitment to the Commission is a basic guarantee for the success of the electronic document management system at the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$, where he confirmed the study (Mohammed, 2004) in terms of a Providing management support contributed to the success of the digital library projects in Egypt, which reached the study (Al Shobaki & others, 2017), (Kassab and others ,2017) and (Al-Sabil, 2003) is that senior management commitment is one of the most important factors for the success of any information or any project system.

Table 14: Arithmetic mean and relative weight

Paragraph	SMA	Relative weight
Senior management commitment to development and support of electronic document management system	3.27	65.4

It is clear from Table 14 that there is a clear adoption by the Authority of the electronic document management system. The average of the arithmetic mean for the total of the axes of this research was 4.16, and the relative weight of the total of the axes was 83.2%.

Testing the hypothesis of the study

The main hypothesis: There is a statistically significant impact of the commitment of the senior management to develop and support the electronic document management system on the success of the electronic document management system in the Palestinian Pension Authority.

To test the hypotheses, the Spearman correlation coefficient and the sign test were used. The results are shown in the table 15:

Table 15: The results of the hypothesis

Hypothesis	Spearman correlation coefficient	Level of significance
H1: There is a statistically significant impact of the commitment of the senior management to develop and support the electronic document management system on the success of the electronic document management system in the Palestinian Pesion Authority.	0.654**	0.000

** The correlation is statistically significant ($\alpha=0.01$)

* The correlation was statistically significant ($\alpha=0.05$)

Proof of the main hypothesis: There is a statistically significant impact of the commitment of the senior management to develop and support the electronic document management system on the success of the electronic document management system in the Palestinian Pension Authority.

It is clear from Table (15) that the correlation coefficient between the commitment of senior management to development and support of the electronic document management system and the success of the electronic document management system is 0.654 and the level of significance is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 indicating rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the hypothesis Which states that it affects the commitment of senior management to develop and support the electronic document management system for the success of electronic document management system. This is due to the importance of senior management commitment to development and support of electronic document management system. Therefore, researchers believe that the role of senior management is the most important requirement for the success of the system, which provides will provide all kinds of support for the success of the system and thus will reap the benefits of the use of this system, which will appear clearly on the work in the Commission in particular and to work with the rest of the external environment, including Which is the most important segment of the Commission's service, and has met with Arafat (2007) a good understanding of decision support systems at the administrative level in PA ministries, which facilitates the use of decision support systems. Al-Ghouti (2006) The requirements for e-government success is having a capable leadership (Abu Khalaf, 2001) found that the majority of supervisors believe that the financial,

administrative, and technical potentials of the project are strong. Al Quds Open University to transform its academic and administrative operations from paper to electronic.

13. RESEARCH RESULTS

1. The existence of a special system includes a written plan and mechanisms for the management of documents at a low rate. Follow-up of the movement of documents issued by the Authority to which a computerized document management system (incoming and outgoing management) is used. The existence of some small accounting systems in some departments to manage documents in the Commission. There is a scientifically qualified and specialized archiving officer.
2. The results confirmed that there is a specialized department to manage the archives of the Commission and this is a high percentage that indicates the existence of departments that are actually managing the archives of the Commission. There is also a unified classification system in document management in the Commission, where there are more than one archive (for retirees, subscribers and each department separately). There is a unified coding system and indexing in the management of documents in the Commission, as the adoption of a coding and indexing system is unified by the Commission where it is agreed to coding and indexing each type of files and not to use international standards in the Commission.
3. There are procedures and mechanisms for the transfer of documents to the Palestinian National Archives at a very low rate because these procedures and mechanisms are not used by the Commission. The percentage of staff who agreed that there is a disaster security plan is 14.3% of the total sample, which is very low due to the existence of fire alarms and the existence of fire extinguishers in the archives and on all floors of the Commission. The percentage of staff who received training in document management and archiving is 2.8% of the total sample, which is very low because of some of the training and after discussion with these employees, researchers found that they received training in document management and archiving in the era of the Israeli Civil Administration of the Gaza Strip.
4. There is a commitment by the senior management Commission in the field of development and support of electronic document management accepted by the system, and as a result of not putting to initiate the application of electronic document management system in the Commission, and poor dissemination of the culture of the use of electronic document management system between the Commission staff, poor access to appropriate mechanisms experiences of other institutions and the private sector with regard to electronic document management system, providing twice the plans for a system of electronic document management and thus a weakness of the staff in the answer to some of the paragraphs of this axis, it was agreed by a good community study that senior management have the ability to provide financial support, the provision of legal limits, providing the latest cutting-edge technology tools for the application of electronic document management system, which emphasizes that senior management's commitment to the Commission is an essential guarantee for the success of the electronic document management system
5. There is a commitment by senior management in the development and support of electronic document management system in all departments and specialties of the Commission, by providing both financial support and the legal limits of the electronic system.

14. RESEARCH RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations can be made:

- Increasing the interest and awareness of the need to apply policies, mechanisms and procedures to ensure the success of the electronic document management system through access to and benefit from the experiences of other institutions and the private sector.
- Enhancing attention to the legislative and legal aspects of electronic transactions through the development of the executive regulations necessary to manage electronic transactions in the Authority.
- Reinforcing the importance of a central computer network linking the main office in Gaza with the rest of the branches in the West Bank in order to ensure the implementation of the electronic document management system and the ability to hold meetings and meetings via videoconferencing and the ability to exchange electronic data copies.
- Promote the interest of the TRA's website and activate it to be able to provide electronic services by linking it to an interactive database, publishing plans, policies, decisions, circulars, objectives, latest activities and news, and creating an e-mail for all employees in order to allow them to e-mail by automating all transactions with the electronic document management system.
- The need to focus on the Palestinian National Archives and follow up international standards by the International Council for Archives (ICA).
- The importance of developing strategic plans and policies to suit the e-government project in the field of electronic document management, so that the central computer network of the Authority is linked to the e-government computer

network in order to ensure the success of the electronic communication process of correspondence and outgoing and incoming between the Authority and the Public Employees Bureau and other ministries, Private sector and universities.

- The need to pay attention to the development of strategic plans and policies and work mechanisms commensurate with the electronic document management system.

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